

Languages, culture, and translation in modern linguistics: comparative approaches
USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN TEACHING VOCABULARY

Botirova Umida

Student, UzSWLU, English Philology faculty

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

[Xaogfdrfy@gmail.com](mailto:xaogfdrfy@gmail.com)

***Abstract.** The article deals with the significance of using real-life in teaching vocabulary. The work shows a number of evidences pointing to the importance of using realia in teaching vocabulary. The actuality of this work is the investigation of real-life activities and authentic materials in teaching vocabulary in the way of development of the vocabulary skills to enrich the word-stock of learners and making EFL classroom more effective teaching environment and its background usage in teaching.*

***Keywords.** Teaching vocabulary, communicative language, ELT materials, foreign language, head Teacher, intelligence, skills.*

Introduction. In these days, the teachers use the communicative approach but using authentic and real-life materials and so on, but we should not forget to use music, films and dramas in class and always interact with our students. Authentic materials reflect the real use of language in culturally appropriate contexts.

The learning of a foreign language is one of the most important requirements in the syllabus of all students, in any area they decide to specialize.

In fact, one of the most spoken languages around the world is the English language. English has become a necessity to develop and understand different aspects of our daily lives for example: at watching TV, at reading books, magazines, at searching for information in internet, to get familiar with food names etc. As a result, the teaching of the English language has emerged and has become part of the school programs at all levels. Exist many factors that are involved in the process of teaching like, the methodology that teachers use to transmit knowledge to students, the materials teachers use to teach the language, the classroom environment, the schedule in which teachers teach, the age of students, the learning styles used by the teachers and the learning strategies used by students.

Considering that the interests of students who learn a foreign language vary from children, teenagers and adults. This paper will emphasize in teaching primary school learners.

Intelligence, skills, emotions, awareness, creativity, purposes, dreams, interests, what is more their own learning styles. Aspects that need to be taken into account when teaching English, in addition to the needs that emerge while teaching in the classroom to young children. Apart from learner, styles there are other problems teachers need to take into consideration such as (the syllabus the institution provides, the methods, materials) these are some difficulties learners face at learning English.

The learning of a foreign language is relevant with pronunciation methods of teaching used by teachers and specific material to learn the English language. In the teaching of a foreign language, children use the communication ability that is typically taught as "school subjects" and the purpose of communication is to understand vocabulary. Statement of the problem English language teaching in our countries has increased in the last decades, in order to have communication with other people. In terms of English teaching, one language aspect taught is vocabulary. Teaching vocabulary to students is very important at any, level of education due to students will be able to express ideas, feelings, emotion and actions. Probably one of teacher problems in primary school learners is that pupils understand what teachers say; they will need an adequate verbal communication, gestures, making movements with their hands, use real objects and materials. Another factor that is considered relevant for teachers to teach English is good selection of, learning styles, methods and adequate materials for children. This study will focus on the use of authentic and real objects to increase and to improve use of the vocabulary in a primary class. In the past the traditional strategy to teach vocabulary involved pre-teaching list of words, copying down definition from the board, and children spending endless hours looking up definition from dictionaries. These activities did not motivate children to understand the topic clearly. Fortunately, English teachers, who work in kindergarten, have different purposes

of teaching. That is the reason this project was created to help teachers include the use of materials for teaching English in primary school. As a result this project is based on the following aspects: English teachers in primary school need more material to teach in a correct manner. And always use concrete materials to teach students as well as (remember)activities to get movements as games and songs; and finally can help students describe what they have learned. English teachers in primary school need more time to do their activities.

Conclusion. In my opinion, real-life and authentic material is a motivating generator so that students can be involved in the lesson. It is important to keep in mind that anything that helps us to have better classes is worthy. The principal purpose of this study is that student's development the communication skill that is a vital part of the learning process. Hence the teacher can use some real material for that children could show positive attitudes in different activities and this can be a great in terms of the teacher-pupil relationship. In addition the teacher can create and adopt authentic material to teach vocabulary as a foreign language so that the children have a great imagination and they could create the activities in fantasy and reality. Indeed the teacher could demonstrate the advantage of authentic material in the teaching.

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